

Establishing the Reliability of Data Collection Instruments.

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Abstract

As a graduation requirement, students often carry out research which must be presented and defended. In this process, related data is gathered using relevant instruments which must satisfy technical properties of validity and reliability. A widespread practice in most institutions is that the researcher validates the instrument through experts' scrutiny for only face and content, and perhaps construct validity without recourse to reliability. However, most research works contain sections addressing the instrument's reliability, with quoted high indices or coefficients obtained from faulty procedures for establishing reliability. This paper examined the reliability of data collection instruments, the types of reliability, when to use them and methods of computing them with the appropriate statistical tools. It was suggested among others, that the inclusion of reliability procedures during instrument validation for data collection, and internal consistency should be emphasised.

Keywords: Reliability, data, instrument, internal consistency, statistical tools.

Introduction

Data collection instruments are generally referred to as research instruments. A research instrument is any tool the researcher may use to collect or obtain data, measure data or analyse data that is relevant to the subject of the research. Often, when graduate students are to carry out their final research (thesis or dissertation), the variables of the study are measured or the data related to the variable is collected either by using predesigned or self-structured instruments. Where predesigned instruments are adapted, some cases may require modifications to properly address the variables in question. When this happens and particularly when a self-structured (by the researcher) instrument is to be used, some technical properties must be established particularly validity and reliability. A very common practice in most institutions, is that the researcher validates the instrument through experts' scrutiny. Unfortunately, more often than not, such experts only scrutinize face, content and perhaps construct validity, without recourse to reliability, without which no instrument can be claimed to be valid or to have been adequately validated.

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Reliability is the consistency of scores obtained by the same persons when they are re-examined with the same test on different occasions, with different sets of equivalent items, or under other variable examining conditions (Anastassi & Urbina, 2006). Koul (2018) described a reliable instrument as one that must have the ability to consistently yield the same results when repeated measurements are taken of the same individuals under the same conditions. Koul (2018) went further to cite Freeman who partitioned reliability into two closely related but somewhat different connotations in psychological testing. Freeman advanced that reliability first refers to the extent to which a measuring device is internally consistent; that is, the consistency of results obtained throughout the measuring device (testing) when administered once. In other words, how accurately is the device measuring at a particular time? Secondly, reliability refers to the extent to which a measuring device yields consistent results upon testing and retesting. That is, how dependable is it for future or predictive purposes? Freeman's position describes internal consistency (stability) and consistency (stability) over time.

Referring to Cronbach, Obilor (2018) defined reliability mathematically, as the proportion of variability in the response to a survey that is the result of differences in the opinion of respondents. To him, a test score is said to be reliable when there is a reason (high proportion) to believe that the score is stable. In this mathematical sense, reliability could be seen as the probability that a product, system or service will perform its intended function adequately for a specified period, or will operate in a defined environment without failure. The higher the probability, the more reliable the device that produces the result. From the foregoing, it is suggestive that reliability simply refers to the stability, constancy, consistency, dependability, reproducibility and trustworthiness of a system, a measuring device or a product or a service to perform the function for which it is meant without failure.

Most of the research methodologies as a practice, contain a section addressing reliability of the instrument, with quoted indices or coefficients of reliability. But when a test expert's scrutiny is done, often it is found that the procedure for establishing the reliability is faulty which inadvertently, invalidates the instrument. Given the above, this paper reviewed the methods for establishing the reliability of instruments used for data collection.

Theory of Reliability

The goal of reliability theory is to estimate errors in measurement and to suggest ways of improving measuring devices (including psychological tests) so that errors are minimized. The central assumptions of the reliability theory are that:

- (i) Measurement errors are essentially random.
- (ii) Observed scores of any measurement comprises two components: -
the true (or internal) component and the error (external) component.

The theory of error component and true component in a test score is represented by

$$X = t + e \quad \text{-----} \quad (1)$$

Where:

- X = Observed score
t = True (internal) component
e = Error (external) component

Factors associated with variations within individuals or subjects from time to time culminate into the internal (true) component, while the external component could be due to the administration of the test to the individual. The reliability theory, thus, provides empirical means of determining the reliability of an instrument or a measuring device as follows:

- i. A perfect (error-free) instrument gives a true (internal) component, as an error component can either be positive or negative, the algebraic sum of the errors being zero if the instrument is administered to a subject in an infinite number of times.
- ii. True component is the mean of the infinite number of times which may practically be impossible. However, from the classical test theory, psychometricians have shown that administering an instrument to a subject in an infinite number of times (several times) and administering it to an infinite number of subjects (several subjects) at once, yield the same result.
- iii. Since the observed score is a combination of true and error components, the variance of the observed score may also be partitioned into two components. Thus, the variance of the observed score of a large group of subjects is a combination of the variance of the true score and the variance of the error of measurement; algebraically given as:

$$sX^2 = st^2 + se^2 \quad \text{-----} \quad (2)$$

Where:

$$sX^2 = \text{Variance of observed score}$$

$$st^2 = \text{Variance of true score}$$

$$se^2 = \text{Variance of error score}$$

In other words, reliability can be expressed as the proportion of the variance in the observed score that is error free.

Since $sX^2 = st^2 + se^2$ then,

$$\frac{\alpha X^2}{\alpha X^2} = \frac{\alpha^2 + \alpha e^2}{\alpha X^2}, \quad \text{-----} \quad (3)$$

The right-hand side of (3) has a common denominator, and transposing equation (3) for the true score variance gives

$$1 - \frac{\alpha e^2}{\alpha X^2} = \frac{\alpha^2}{\alpha X^2} = r \quad \text{-----} \quad (4)$$

and this defines the coefficient of reliability (r).

Thus, reliability is given by the ratio of the true (internal) score variance to the observed score variance, that is:

$$r = \frac{\alpha^2}{\alpha X^2} .$$

Equation 4 indicates that the reliability coefficient can always be a value ranging from - 1.00 to + 1.00 for perfect negative and perfect positive coefficients respectively. The degree of departure of the correlation coefficient from 1.00 shows the error.

Factors affecting Reliability

- i. Error of Measuring Instrument: Test length (the longer the test, the better for adequate coverage of content), difficulty level (moderate difficulty is advisable), ambiguity of items (ambiguous wording of the items should be avoided) and optional items (the same testee may not attempt the same items on a second administration).

- ii. Error of Administration: Inconsistency in administration resulting from inexperience examiners, time interval (between two administrations - time should not be too long and not too short), and unconducive environment (noisy, poor ventilation, poor lightening, inadequate spacing of examinees).
- iii. Examinees Error: Lack of motivation, lack of interest, fatigue, lack of or poor writing materials, etc.
- iv. Error of Scorer: Generosity, severity, objectivity or subjectivity of the scorer influences the reliability of the instrument.
- v. Halo Effect: a cognitive bias where an overall impression or trait influences judgments of specific characteristics. In other words, the good/bad impression a respondent formed about a concept, item, person, or issue being measured, can influence his/her rating of that phenomenon being measured (Obilor, 2018).
- vi. Hawthorne effect: the awareness or knowledge that one is being tested (observed or measured) influences the testees' responses.

Methods of Estimating Reliability (Reliability Indices)

The reliability or stability of a measuring device can be expressed as a correlation coefficient or an index of correlation. According to Ojoko (2004), Best and Kahn (2006), Siegle (2013), Asuru (2016) and Obilor (2018), the reliability or stability of a measuring device can be established over *Time* (Test Retest), over *Samples* (Equivalent or Parallel or Alternative Form), over *Items* (Internal Consistency), over *Scorers* (Interscorer or Interrater) and over *Testers* (Inter tester).

The concept of reliability types can be represented with the framework below:

Fig. 1: Framework of Reliability Types

The pentagon at the centre of Figure 1 depicts reliability, surrounded by the different types showcased in triangles on each side of the pentagon. The rectangles represent the procedures used to establish the type as further discussed in the next section.

Stability or consistency over time (Test-retest)

This approach measures errors due to changes over time.

Procedure: The same instrument is administered twice or more times to the same group of subjects, and using appropriate procedures (e.g. Person’s Product Moment Correlation - PPMC), the scores are correlated to obtain the reliability of the instrument.

- Uses:**
- (i) When the interest is to rule out errors due to changes over time
 - (ii) The instrument is intended for predictive purposes

A major drawback of this method is the memory effect, practice and the confidence induced by familiarity with test materials in the first administration which may overestimate the test reliability if the time lag is too short; on the other hand, the real changes in behaviour in terms of growth may under-estimate the reliability, if the time is too long. Owing to the difficulty in controlling conditions which influence test scores on the second administration, the test-retest method is generally less useful than the other methods (Koul 2018). Nevertheless, if the instrument is intended for continuous use over time, then the test rest is a major asset.

Stability over item samples (parallel or equivalent or alternative form)

In this case, two or more equivalent forms are combined and given as one longer test, the items are separated later for scoring. Alternatively, the same person can be tested with one form on the first occasion and with another equivalent form on the second. Again with appropriate procedures, the correlation index between the scores obtained on the forms represents the reliability coefficient of the test.

- Uses:**
- (i) When the researcher is interested in the consistency of scores among samples of a pool.
 - (ii) When samples are closely related in characteristics such that can be used interchangeably.

Time and testers are no issues here because the versions are given without time lag.

Fig. 2: Pool of Alternative Forms

Figure 2 illustrates alternative or parallel or equivalent test samples to one another. In other words, once reliability is established for all samples, and can be used as an alternative or equivalent to the other.

Stability over tester (Inter-examiner reliability)

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This reliability demonstrates that two different trained testers can administer the same test to the same group of people and not have their personality, or other attributes affect the results.

Procedure: It is like a test-retest, but here, two or more different examiners (testers) administer the tests, with each one giving the test the first half of the time. Appropriate correlation procedures are applied to obtain the reliability index.

Uses: When the interest is to see the effect on test scores if different examiners are used to administer a test at different times.

Stability over scorers (Inter-rater reliability)

Inter-scorer reliability measures the extent to which data collectors (multiple observers) assign the same score to the same variable.

Procedure: Two or more observers make observations and record behaviours or collect data. Reliability across multiple observers is termed interrater, and reliability with a single-data-collector deals with whether a single observer will report the same value each time the same situation and phenomenon is presented.

Uses: (i) When performance and product are to be assessed (e.g. audition).

(ii) To avoid the problem of single-observer uncertainties or idiosyncrasies.

Disagreement is likely to arise among observers' records and interpretations of behaviours, despite the best effort at using well-trained observers and well-defined objectives, hence the need to establish stability or consistency over scorers.

Several statistics have been used to measure interrater and interrater reliability among which are: Percent agreement for the number of times observers agree, Cohen's kappa (for two observers), Fleiss' kappa (adaptation of Cohen's kappa for 3 or more observers), Gwet's AC2 Coefficient, Krippendorff's Alpha (used when there are multiple raters and possible multiple ratings), intra-class correlation coefficient, and the concordance correlation coefficient (Stephanie Glen, 2016).

Stability over Items (Internal or Inter-Items Consistency)

Internal consistency measures consistency within the instrument (consistency among the items). Several methods of internal consistency exist but with the common denominator that the subjects complete one form only at a time. From a single administration of one form, it is possible to arrive

at measures of reliability using various split-half procedures. Cronbach's Alpha, however, is the most commonly used for measuring internal consistency especially when the instrument uses the Likert-type rating.

- Uses:**
- (i) Establishes the extent the scale measures the intended construct.
 - (ii) Identifies items that do not fit with the rest of the scale (item biases)
 - (iii) Can be used to establish reliability over time (Test-retest).
 - (iv) Used to compare instruments that measure the same construct.
 - (v) Scale refinement: used to identify and remove items not contributing to the reliability of the scale

Computation of Reliability Coefficients:

Reliability coefficients can be computed using different statistical procedures among which are Percent Agreement, Cohen's kappa (k), Kuder Richardson formula 20 and 21 (KR₂₀ & KR₂₁), Split-Half, and Spearman's Prophecy or Guttman Lambda 4 (λ₄), Cronbach's Alpha (α) and Pearson's Product Moment Correlation (r).

Percent Agreement: Like a simple percentage, the method involves counting the number of times observers agreed and dividing it by the total number of observations. Specifically, Percent Agreement is given by.

$$\frac{\text{Total number of agreement}}{\text{Total number of observations}} \times 100 \quad \text{-----} \quad (5)$$

Although Percent Agreement is a simple way of assessing interrater reliability, a few drawbacks are associated with it. Unless the agreement is loosely defined and not as an exact match, Percent Agreement underestimates interrater agreement. Percent agreement makes no provisions for determining whether the amount of agreement observed is real or due to chance and finally, behaviour that occurs with very high or low frequency may have extremely high levels of chance agreement. In such cases, Percent Agreement over estimates interrater agreement.

For instance, Miwari (2017) in his work "awareness and application of test construction patterns of senior secondary school mathematics teachers", asked two experts (A & B) to classify teachers' past mathematics items into Higher Level and Lower Level cognitive behavioural objectives. The following were their observations/classification:

A and B agreement on Lower Level	=	12000
A and B agreement on Higher Level	=	1400
Disagreement A (Higher Level) B (Lower Level)	=	71
_____Disagreement A (Lower Level) B (Higher Level)	=	590
=====Total		14061

The interrater reliability by Percent Agreement, therefore, was:

$$\frac{12000 + 1400}{14061} \times 100 = \frac{13400}{14061} \times 100$$

$$= \mathbf{95\%}$$

This is quite a high Percent Agreement. However, in most practical cases, a Percent Agreement of around 70% is acceptable.

Cohen’s Kappa Reliability Coefficient (K): This was developed to account for the probability that observers can actually guess on at least some variables as a result of uncertainties (Bordens & Abbott, 2002). To use this method, the proportion of actual agreement between observers (actual agreement) and the proportion of agreement expected by chance (expected agreement) must be determined. These two values are then applied to the Cohen’s Kappa formula given by:

$$K = \frac{P_o - P_c}{1 - P_c} \text{-----} \quad (6)$$

Where:

K is Cohen’s Kappa coefficient of reliability

P_o is the observed proportion of actual agreement

P_c is the chance proportion of expected agreement

Cohen’s Kappa computation requires the tabulation of frequencies of agreement and disagreement between raters in a confusion matrix (Bakemann & Gottman, cited in Bordens & Abbott, 2002).

An agreement occurs whenever both observers classify behaviour in the same way. Using the same data as in Percent Agreement above, Cohen’s Kappa reliability coefficient can be computed as shown below:

Table 1: Cohen’ Kappa Confusion Matrix

		Observer (Expert) A		
Observer (Expert) B	Lower level	Lower Level	Higher Level	Total
		12,000	71	12,071
	Higher level	590	1,400	1,990
Total		12,590	1,471	14,061

$$P_c = \frac{(12590 \times 12071) + (1471 \times 1990)}{(14061)^2} = 0.78$$

$$P_o = \frac{12000 + 1400}{14061} = 0.95$$

$$K = \frac{0.95 - 0.78}{1 - 0.78} = 0.77$$

Cohen suggested that a Kappa (K) of 0.61 – 0.80, within which the above result lies will be interpreted as substantial. Accordingly, there was substantial agreement in the Experts’ classification above hence the question paper was reliable.

Split Half

Scores in odd-numbered items can be correlated with scores on even-numbered items, and scores in the first half can be correlated with scores in the second half. The second alternative is most applicable when the items are equally difficult throughout the test, a condition hardly attained in testing.

The number of possible splits is given by:

$$C(2r,r)/2 \text{ or } \frac{{}^n C_r / 2}{{}^{(n-r)} |r| / 2} \quad {}^n C_r / 2, \quad n = 2r; \text{ for even number items} \quad (7)$$

$$C(2r+1,r), \text{ or } {}^n C_r, n = 2r+1, \text{ for odd number items.} \tag{8}$$

For instance, if n or 2r is 10, number of possible splits is

$${}^{10}C_5 / 2 = 10! / [(10-5)!5! \times 2] = 10 \times 9 \times 8 \times 7 \times 6 / 5 \times 4 \times 3 \times 2 \times 1 \times 2 = 21 \times 6 = 126$$

If n = 2r+1 is 9, number of possible splits is

$${}^9C_4 = 9! / (9-4)!4! = 9 \times 8 \times 7 \times 6 / 4 \times 3 \times 2 \times 1 = 126$$

Spearman-Brown Prophecy Formula (Predicted Reliability)

Correlation arising from split half is only for one half of the test, hence to make up for the whole, bearing in mind that the longer the test, the better (Annastassi & Urbina 2006), Spearman-Brown provides the Prophecy (correction) formula given by:

$$r_x = \frac{2r}{1+r}, \text{ for two equal halves} \tag{8}$$

Where: r_x = estimated reliability of the entire test.

r = reliability of half of a test found by means of the split-half technique

For two unequal halves, the following formula is applied:

$$r_x = \frac{r(\sqrt{r^2 + 2c(1-r^2)} - r)}{c(1-r^2)}, (r \neq \pm 1) \tag{9}$$

Where:

$$C = 2p(1-p) \tag{10}$$

p = proportion of test due to the first half

Note: If the two halves are equal then

$$C = 2(0.5)(1-0.5) = 2(0.5)(0.5) = 0.5 \text{ and if this is substituted for c in}$$

formula (9) and evaluated, the result will be formula (8).

Cronbach’s alpha

Lee Cronbach, provides a modified model for determining the reliability coefficient given by:

$$r = \frac{n}{n-1} \left(1 - \frac{\sum S_i^2}{S_i^2} \right) \text{-----} \tag{11}$$

Where:

r = Cronbach’s alpha reliability coefficient

n = Number of items in the score

$\sum S_i^2$ = Sum of the item variances

S_i^2 = Total test score Variance

Cronbach’s Alpha assesses reliability by comparing the amount of shared variance or covariance among the items making up an instrument to the amount of overall variance. The idea is that if the instrument is reliable, there should be a great deal of covariance among items relative to the variance. Cronbach’s Alpha is equivalent to taking the average of all possible split-half reliabilities. For instance, the hypothetical data below is the response of eight testees to a five-item questionnaire on their perception of statistics as a core course in education. The scoring was 4 = strongly agreed, 3 = Agreed, 2 = disagreed and 1 = strongly disagreed. It is required that the reliability of the instrument is determined using Cronbach’s alpha.

Table 1: Computation of Cronbach’s alpha

Student	1	2	3	4	5	Total
A	3	1	2	4	3	13
B	2	3	3	4	3	15
C	2	2	2	1	2	9
D	4	2	4	3	4	17
E	3	3	4	2	1	13
F	4	4	1	3	4	16
G	3	3	3	1	3	13
H	2	4	2	4	2	14
	23	22	21	22	22	110

$$\text{VAR} = \quad 0.70 \quad 1.07 \quad 1.13 \quad 1.64 \quad 1.07 \quad 13.8$$

$$\sum S_i^2 = \quad 5.61$$

$$S_t^2 = \quad 5.93$$

$$Y_x = r = \frac{n}{n-1} \left(1 - \frac{\sum S_i^2}{S_t^2} \right) = r = \frac{5}{4} \left(1 - \frac{5.61}{5.93} \right)$$

$$Y_x = \quad 0.07$$

The Split-half Approach (Guttman and PPMC or SROC)

Besides the commonly known PPMC and Spearman-Brown prophesy adopted with split halves, Guttman lambda 4 (λ_4) is one alternative index that has been proposed as superior to Cronbach’s alpha (α) (Tom Benton, 2015). While Cronbach’s α may underestimate the reliability, Guttman may overestimate especially if the number of items is large or the sample size is small. However, Guttman λ_4 considers the maximal lambda (Max λ) from all possible split halves. Gottman λ_4 is given by:

$$\lambda = \frac{4 \text{cov}(h_1, h_2)}{\text{var}(t)} \quad \text{-----} \quad (12)$$

Where: h_1 = partial scores from the first half

h_2 = partial scores from the second half

t = the total scores

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Each split half will produce a different value of λ while the Guttman reliability is defined as:

$$\lambda_{\max} = \max \{ \lambda : \text{all possible split halves} \}. \quad \text{-----} \quad (13)$$

Using the data from the hypothetical case above, a typical split, Guttman lambda and PPMC (with the appropriate correction formula) are demonstrated. The typical split shown in table 2 is item 1 (odd), item 3 (odd), item 5 (odd), item 2 (even) and item 4 (even); represented by 00011 in column 2 of table 3.

Table 2: Guttman Lambda (λ_4) and PPMC (r_x)

Student	ODD,ODD,ODD,EVEN-EVEN (1,3,5,2,4)					Odd	Even	Total		
	1	2	3	4	5					
A	3	1	2	4	3	8	5	13	COVAR	-
B	2	3	3	4	3	8	7	15	VAR	0.2857
C	2	2	2	1	2	6	3	9	LAMBD	5.9285
D	4	2	4	3	4	12	5	17	A	7
E	3	3	4	2	1	8	5	13	PPMC	-
F	4	4	1	3	4	9	7	16	r =	0.1928
G	3	3	3	1	3	9	4	13	r _x =	-
H	2	4	2	4	2	6	8	14		0.0886
Total					110.0	C=0.4				
Total					0	P=0.6	8			

The respective sums of odd and even items for each student are shown on the odd and even columns, $p = 0.6$ and $c = 0.48$ are the proportions of odd and even items while the covariance of odd and even items (COVAR) is -0.2857, the variance of the total items (VAR) is 5.92857 and the Lambda (λ_4) computed value is -0.1928. Using PPMC with the same split, the correlation (r) index for the half items is -0.0886 and for the total test (employing spear Brown prophecy formula 8), is $r_x = -0.1987$, almost the same with Guttman lambda value.

The different possible splits of the five items (formula 6) is shown in table 3. The second column shows the different splits, column three shows the items arrangement while columns four and five are the respective lambda and PPMC indices obtained.

Table 3: Summary of Some Splits, Lambda and PPMC Values

	SPLITS	ITEMS	λ_4	PPMC (r_x)	
1	00011	13524	-0.1928	-0.1987	
2	01010	12345	0	0	
3	01100	12435	0.27711	0.29763	
4	01001	12534	-0.012	-0.0127	
5	00110	13425	0.28916	0.29986	
6	10100	23415	0.03614	0.03676	
7	11000	24513	-0.1928	-0.2153	
8	10001	23514	0.51807	0.52395	
9	01001	34512	0.22892	0.24636	
1					$\lambda_4=0.5$
0	01010	14523	-0.3012	-0.367	2

Source: EXCEL Spreadsheet data.

The value of 0.52 and above is acceptable since it is the maximum as defined by Gottman. Notice that the lambda values and the PPMC values almost correspond for each of the arrangement. The challenge is the patience to go through the permutation and combination to get the best arrangement for the maximum values. For the above, arrangement 8 (items 2,3,5,1 and 4) makes the test most reliable.

Kuder-Richardson formula 20 (K-R₂₀) and Kuder-Richard formula 21 (K-R₂₁).

These are alternative formulae for estimating internal consistency of subjects’ responses among the items on an instrument. Items on the instrument must be binary items scored as 0 for incorrect and 1 for correct. All items are compared with each other, rather than half of the items. Kuder Richardson formula results in the average correlation of all possible split halves. The method estimates the reliability without using correlational procedures, but rather, multiplies the correct answer with wrong answer and adding them up. The two versions of the formulae are named Kuder

Richardson formula 20 and 21. KR₂₁ assumes that the binary items must be of equal difficulty (a condition hardly attained).

$$K-R_{20}; g_{11} = \frac{n}{n-1} \left(\frac{\sigma^2 - \sum Pq}{\sigma^2} \right) \text{-----} \quad (14)$$

$$K-R_{21}; g_{11} = \frac{K\sigma^2 - \bar{X}(K - \bar{X})}{\sigma^2(K-1)} \text{-----} \quad (15)$$

Where: g_{11} = Reliability of the entire test

K or n = Number of items in the test

s^2 = Variance of the scores

\bar{X} = Mean of the scores (x_i are the scores)

p = Proportion of the right answers

q = Proportion of wrong answers

The following represents the responses of six students to five items that were dichotomously scored (1 - yes, 0 - No). The test reliability is determined using the Kuder-Richardson formula as presented below:

Table 4: Demonstration of KR₂₀

Student	Items					X	p	q	pq
	1	2	3	4	5				
A	1	1	1	0	1	4	0.8	0.2	0.16
B	1	0	1	0	1	3	0.6	0.4	0.24
C	0	0	1	1	1	3	0.6	0.4	0.24

D	1	1	0	1	1	4	0.8	0.2	0.16
E	0	1	0	1	1	3	0.6	0.4	0.24
F	1	1	0	0	0	2	0.4	0.6	0.24
						$\Sigma X=19$	$\Sigma pq=1.28$		

Variance of scores $s^2 = \{n \Sigma X^2 - (\Sigma X)^2\} / \{n(n-1)\} = 2.3$

Number of items $n = 5$

$$KR_{20} g_{11} = 5/4 \{1 - (1.28/2.3)\}$$

$$= 5/4 \times 0.44 = 0.57$$

This is just a moderately reliable test as the minimal acceptable value is 0.8.

It is noteworthy that KR_{21} is applicable when the items of the scale are of equal difficulty (Bordens & Abbott, 2002).

Required test forms and test sessions for reliability procedures are presented in the table below:

Table 1: Test Forms and Test Sessions Required for Reliability Procedures

Testing Sessions Required	Test Forms Required	
	One	Two or more
One	Split Half Kuder-Richardson Cronbach's alpha	Equivalent (Parallel/ Alternative) Form, Inter rater or scorer,
Two or more	Test-retest Inter Examiner or Tester	

Source: (Anastassi and Urbina in Koul, 2018).

Conclusion

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Having established that an instrument cannot be valid without first being reliable, and an invalid instrument used for data collection automatically invalidates a work, it could be inferred that most faults found after students' works have been accepted for graduation, are a result of inadequately validated instrument resulting from unreliability. It is worth observing that the reliability of any instrument can be improved by increasing the number of items in the instrument and a carefully designed administrative direction, plus an appropriate procedure for establishing reliability for the instrument.

Suggestions

The following are suggestions for improving the reliability of data collection instruments:

- i. The instrument to be validated must be accompanied by procedures for establishing the reliability of the instrument.
- ii Validation of the instrument should not be done in the absence of the researcher who should necessarily defend the objectives of the study.
- iii Emphasis should be placed on the internal consistency of all data collection instruments
- iv. Every validation of a data collection device should involve a test expert

REFERENCES

Anastasi, A & Urbina (2006). *Psychological Testing (7th ed.)*. India: Dorling Kindersley.

Asika, N (2006). *Research Methodology in the Behavioural Sciences*. Lagos: Longman Nigeria Ltd.

Asuru, V. A. (2016). *Measurement and Evaluation in Education and Psychology (2nd Ed.)*. Port Harcourt: Pearl Publishers International Ltd

Best, J.W. & Kahn, J.V. (2006). *Research in Education (9th ed.)*. India: Dorling Kindersley.

Bordens, K. S. & Abbott, B.B. (2002). *Research Designs and Methods: A Process Approach*. Mexico City: Mcgraw- Hill Higher Education.

Glen, S (2016): Interrater Reliability IRR: Definitions, Calculations. Retrieved April 05, 2023, from <https://www.statisticshowto.com/interrater-reliability/>.

Koul, L. (2018). *Methodology of Educational Research*. New Delhi: VIKAS Publishing House PVT Ltd

McHugh, M. L.(2018). Interrater Reliability: The Kappa Statistics. Retrieved from www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov on April 18, 2023

Miwari, G. U. (2017). *Awareness and Application of Test Construction Patterns of Senior Secondary School Mathematics Teachers*. Unpublished Master's Thesis. Rivers State University, Nkpolu Oroworukwo, Port Harcourt

Obilor, E. I. (2018). *Fundamental of Research Methods and Statistics in Education and Social Sciences*. Port Harcourt: SABCOS Printers and Publishers

Ojoko, S.S. (2004). *Measurement and Evaluation in Teacher Education*. Owerri: Springfield Publishers.

Siegle, D. (2013). Educational Research Basics. Retrieved from <https://researchbasics.education.uconn.edu> on February 18, 2023

Stephanie, G. (2016). Interrater Reliability IRR: Definitions, Calculations. Retrieved from <https://www.statistichouse.com> on March 24, 2023.

Zaiontz, C. (2023). Real Statistics using EXCEL. Retrieved from <https://www.realstatistics.com> on April 4, 2023